

Extraction of per-fluorinated alkyl substances using ionic liquids and porous solid matrices

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Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are a subgroup of aliphatic fluorinated substances composed of one or more carbon atoms in their structure, where the hydrogen substituents are replaced by fluorine. These substances are highly harmful to humans, animals, and the environment because they accumulate and are persistent and toxic in different media such as water, soil, and air. High exposure levels to these compounds increase the risk of dangerous health issues for humans, such as kidney and testicular cancer, thyroid problems, and reduction of the effectiveness of vaccines in infants, among others. The objective of this work is to evaluate the capacity of fluorinated ionic liquids (FILs) and porous solid matrices, such as activated carbons, to extract per-fluorinated alkyl substances in aqueous solution. For this purpose, FILs were synthesized, and the extraction capabilities were analysed. The results are promising, opening a very interesting path to the optimization of a more sustainable process of PFAS water treatment, which helps to solve one of the current environmental and health issues of great concern in Europe achieving a cleaner environment for the species and ensuring the well-being of species.

References

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